

Faleronymous names are based on nominative - motivational principles

Khusanova Maksuda Nishonovna

Renaissance Educational University

Senior teacher of the Department of Philology

Abstract

In the article, the faleronym names are based on the nominative-motivational principle and motivated, as well as their lexical-semantic analysis.

Key words: faleronym, naming, sign, feature, activity, incentive, reward, reward.

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Phaleronyms are names of orders, medals, badges and awards that are the product of intellectual, intellectual and artistic activity of a person. When giving a name to phaleronim, their unique characteristics were taken as a motivation. Motive means the basis, symbol chosen by namers to name the object. In the process of naming phaleronyms, the known activity is important. The namer chooses one of the signs of the named object, or one of his imaginations, dreams, and wishes about it. Therefore, in naming the awards, well-known activities and characteristics are important. We will pay attention to the meaning of the word reward, which is one of the types of faleronym. The word "Prize" was adopted from Arabic to Uzbek and means "appreciation", "payment": "A form of incentive for special achievements in a field of activity (valuable item, money, medal, order, etc.). High award. State award. Prize money. Give a reward. Get a reward. To present for an award"[1].

Awards are also one of the tools that motivate people to new achievements. They are divided into the following types: 1) ordinary reward - a type of incentive given before the holiday and for good work in workplaces; 2) awards given by the ministry and hokimiyat - certificates of commendation, letters of thanks, certificates of honor and awards based on material funds;

3) certificates of honor, letters of thanks given to encourage pupils, students, graduate students and their teachers in the educational system; 4) state awards are one of the means of motivating people by the state. This award is one of the highest among other awards. On October 28, 2000, the State Prize of the Republic of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, the State Prize of the Republic of Uzbekistan named after Abu Raikhan Beruni, and others were accepted. In some cases, they are graded: State Award of the first degree, State Award of the second degree, State Award of the third degree; 5) State award to creative writers and poets. Such awards are still being given. They include State Prize named after Hamid Olimjon, State Prize named after Abdulla Qadiri, State Prize named after Cholpon, State Prize named after Zulfiya. The State Prize of Uzbekistan named after Hamza was established and awarded to artists who worked in poetry, cinema and theater.

The faleronym "Muhammad al-Khorazmi" is named after the great mathematician, astronomer and geographer, founder of the science of algebra, Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khorazmi. The word "algebra" is taken from his treatise "Al-kitab al-mukhtasar fi lisab al-jabr wa al-muqabala".

This award is given individually to scientists, including foreign citizens and stateless persons, who proposed a solution to a specific problem in practice based on the results of their

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fundamental and applied scientific research in the field of mathematics. The award may be made to an individual for one or more achievements in mathematics. The dignonym "Muhammad Al-Khorazmi" lexically consists of two words. Muhammad is the name of the prophet, and the 47th sura of the Holy Qur'an is named after them. Since the 8th century, he has been mentioned in the literature as the first propagator of Islam and the messenger of Allah. Muhammad means praiseworthy. This name is derived from the Arabic root "hamd". This name is based on praise[2]. The name Khorezmi is based on the name of the place. If Klippert and Lerx interpret the name of the toponym "Khorazm" as "low flat land", Burnuf, Zahau, Zeiger as "fertile land", or on the contrary, Yusta and Spiegel interpret it as "bad, barren land", researchers interpret the toponym with the word Hurr, Horsed, "sun". connect and interpret Khorezm as the "land of the sun"[3]. According to S.P. Tolstov, it is probably related to the name of the tribe-Khurrit, one of the founders of the Mitanni state in Ancient Asia, meaning Khorezm-"Khvari-zem" (land, land of the Hurrians)[4]. Often, after toponyms, the suffix -iy is added to form nisbas. In this case, it is formed from the names of towns and villages with the suffix - ий. Khorezm, Bukhari, etc. Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khwarazmi means that he is from Khorazmi, the son of Muhammad Musa.

"Imam Bukhari" order. On August 15, 2022, the President of Uzbekistan signed the law on the establishment of the Order of Imam Bukhari. According to the law, the order of "Imam Bukhari" consists of two levels: 1. "High-ranking Imam Bukhari" order; 2. "Imam Bukhari" order.

One of the religious dignonyms is the "Imam Bukhari" order. His real name was Abdullah Muhammad ibn Ismail ibn Ibrahim ibn al-Mughira ibn Bardizbah al-Bukhari al-Jafi. Because he was born in Bukhara, he was given the Bukhari nisab. He made a great contribution to the development of hadith science. He wrote his works and all the information he collected with his own hand. Imam al-Bukhari's collection "Al-jami' as-sahih" (Reliable collection of hadiths) is used as the main source after the Holy Qur'an. During the creation of this collection, he collected about six hundred thousand hadiths, of which about three hundred thousand are "sahih" and two hundred thousand are "non-sahih". divided into sahih" and knew them by heart. Imam Bukhari created more than twenty works during his academic career. He died in the village of Khartang, Payariq district, Samarkand region. "Imam" is an Arabic word meaning "Leader standing in front", the word "Imam" has been actively used since the 14th century. It has the following meanings: 1. The great leader of all Muslims in Islam. Imam Muhammad. 2. Founders of sects in Islam. Imam Azam. 3. Famous scholars Hujjat ul-Islam Imam Muhammad Ghazali. The word imam is a title that means leader of the clergy, imam of the mosque, religious servant, and mullah.

An anthroponym is made from a Bukhari-toponym to form a dignonym. It is indicated that he was born in the city of Bukhara. Nishopuri's book "Khazain ul-Ulum" expressed the following opinion about Bukhara: now Bukhara (settled) is a mawze, (previously) a swamp, some of its lands were orchards, orchards and green fields, and some places were such that even an animal had a place to set foot. could not find. The reason for this is that in the regions on the Samarkand side, the snow melts in the mountains and the water (flows) accumulates there. The name Bukhara appears in the works of the historian Nasharkhi in the 10th century. According to linguists, the word Bukhara comes from the ancient Indo-Sanskrit word "Vihara" which means "Fortress". This city was also called Numijkat and Fakhira[6].

The State Prize named after Alisher Navoi was established on September 13, 1989. This award is given to the brightest and most meaningful works in the field of literature, art and architecture, which are a special example in the cultural life of the country and enrich the treasury

of national values. Alisher Navoi wrote in two languages. He gave the pseudonyms Foni to his works in Persian, and Navoiy to his works written in Turkish.

He wrote the historical work "Tarihi muluki Ajam" ("History of the Kings of Ajam"), the review "Majolis un-nafais" ("Complex of the Nobles"), and the scientific book "Mezon ul-Awzon" ("Measure of Weights") about aruz weight. book, book "Khazayin ul-maani" ("Treasure of Meanings"), epic "Lison ut-tayr" ("Language of birds") and scientific work "Muhokamat ul-lughatayn" ("Discussion of two languages") created

Especially Alisher Navoi's epic "Khamsa" is enriched with themes of advice, love, loyalty, loyalty, patriotism, hard work. The work is famous for being written in Turkish in verse and prose. The principle of naming this faleronim is positive (positive). If we pay attention to Falereonim's analysis: Alisher (ar.-ft.) means to be brave and courageous like a lion and to be supported by Ali[7]. This name consists of two parts, Ali and lion. Ali is an Arabic word that means "high", "great", "exalted", [8] and "sher" means "brave", "lion", "strong" in Persian. Because Ali is the caliph, this name is widespread in Islamic countries. For his heroism and bravery in battles, Ali was given the Persian lion title "Haydar". Haydarali means "Lion of Ali Allah". Nickname of Navoi Alisher. The Arabic word "Navo" means "melody", "melody", "mungli un", "lineage", "wealth". So, Navoi's nickname has also become my nickname.

Beruni (Abu Rayhan Beruni) State Award of the Republic of Uzbekistan is an award in the field of science and technology, established on September 6, 1967. It has been awarded as the State Award of the Republic of Uzbekistan since March 5, 1991. Researches and scientific and technical programs of the republic that make a great contribution to the development of science to a certain scientist or group of scientists, are of high practical importance, ensure that the science and technology of the republic reaches the level of world achievements, are widely recognized by the public, and have been published three or more times. is awarded for original textbooks designed for higher educational institutions, incorporating new scientific ideas. Ubaidullo Karimov, a scholar of Beruni, stated that "the scholar's name is Muhammad, his father's name is Ahmed, and Beruni is his name, that is, his origin and lineage." "Beruni" is derived from the Persian word "berun" which means "outside" and "born outside the city". Nickname of Abu Rayhan, which means "merciful", "merciful" in Arabic. Beruni's ratio has also become Faleronim.

"Zulfiya" award. Zulfia's poems expressing the happy fate of Uzbek women and the dreams of people who are thirsty for peace and work are the basis for the name of this award. Zulfia's love for poetry and literature was awakened in her childhood. Her poems were published in various newspapers when she was studying at school and women's pedagogical institute. His first collection of poems is published under the name "Life Leaflets". The main theme of this collection was about youth, love, human heart. He works in various large publishing houses, newspapers and magazines. Zulfia met Hamid Olimjon at the Institute of Language and Literature under the Committee of Sciences of Uzbekistan, their relationship turned into love and they got married. Zulfia works as the editor-in-chief of Saodat magazine, the state publishing house of Uzbekistan. Her husband Hamid Olimjon dies in a car accident. Poems from the poetess's collections "Hayat Jhilosi", "Orik Gulaganda", "Dreams", "Soginish" and other collections dedicated to the memory of Hamid Olimjon reflect feelings and longing. Therefore, the nominative basis of the "Zulfia" award is the exemplary service of women to their family and homeland.

In short, the award is established, determined and awarded by the state. Awards are named on the basis of their characteristics based on the nominative positive principle. Awards increase people's work efficiency, feed them with love for life. Increases public image.

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